

Event metadata

Event title	Globus: moving large volumes of research data with ease
Event type	Webinar
Date of event	13/05/2026
Time of event	12pm AEST
Topic description	<p>Life science research increasingly involves the generation of massive datasets that need to be shared, archived, or moved to high-performance computing environments. Relying on traditional transfer methods is challenging because of slow speeds, issues with data integrity, and connection drops that often require restarting the transfer multiple times. This webinar introduces Globus as a powerful solution for life science researchers to manage these transfers with ease.</p> <p>You will hear firsthand accounts of how life scientists are using Globus for uploading data to repositories like PRIDE, downloading from the ENA, and sharing data with collaborators at facilities such as the QIMR Berghofer Medical Research Institute. We will also explore the core features of Globus, including its ability to maintain data fidelity and security through a user-friendly interface.</p> <p>Finally, the session will explain how AARNet is supporting Globus to solve complex data movement problems. You will learn how to determine if your institution has a subscription and understand the differences between institutional licences and personal endpoints. Whether you are moving gigabytes or terabytes, this session will show you how to take the headache out of data movement.</p>
Format description	Webinar presentation followed by a brief question and answer session
Identifier(s)/URL	https://www.biocommons.org.au/events/globus-2026
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Keywords	Bioinformatics http://edamontology.org/topic_0091 Data transfer Globus Research data AARNet Research infrastructure
Contact	training@biocommons.org.au
Audience	This webinar is for life scientists and bioinformaticians who need reliable methods for transferring large amounts of research data, either across Australia or internationally.
Prerequisites	None
Technical requirements	None
Learning outcomes	By the end of this webinar you should be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify how Globus can be used to maintain data integrity and security during large-scale transfers. • Understand real-world applications of Globus for repository uploads and international collaborations. • Determine how to access institutional Globus subscriptions through AARNet.
Speakers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Greg D’Arcy (AARNet) • Dr Farah Zaib Khan (Australian BioCommons) • Dr Rohan Lowe (La Trobe University) • John Pearson (QIMR Berghofer Medical Research Institute)
Training materials	<p>Materials shared in this Zenodo record:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Globus Zenodo - Event metadata.pdf: Information about the event including, description, event URL, learning objectives, prerequisites, technical requirements etc. • Globus Webinar - Slides.pdf: slides presented during the webinar. <p>Materials shared elsewhere:</p>

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none">Recording of the presentation on the Australian BioCommons YouTube channel: https://youtu.be/-cpPeD9x46Q
Related material	None